

Pet Type Classification And Detection using Convolutional Neural Networks.

Sreelakshmi P

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
sreelakshmip2024b@mca.aice.in

Amal K Jose

Department of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
amalkjose@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Discover the new technology for pets . Find new ways to use artificial intelligence and machine learning to make veterinary care better for animals. We mainly make sure that pets stay healthy. We use modern technology and computers to assist us instead of old-fashioned devices that you wear. Come and learn about how pets are put into categories based on their type, origin, and what makes them different. Come and see how we will be taking care of pets in the future. It is a place where new ideas and kindness work together to make sure all pets are well and happy.

Keywords- - *Pet Breed Classification, Pet Identification, Pet Face Detection, Convolutional Neural Networks, CNNs*

I. INTRODUCTION

Many places, like Thailand, have a big problem with stray animals, like dogs. This problem happens because more and more people are getting pets without knowing how to take care of them properly. This leads to pets being left behind or lost without any way to find them. Old ways to identify pets like collars, microchips, and GPS tags are expensive and can be lost or broken.

To solve this problem, our research looks at a better and less invasive way to use computer programs to get important information from pictures of pets. We are studying how well using pre-trained Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models can help us identify different characteristics of pets, like what type of pet they are, their breed, where they were born, and their skin type, from pictures of the pets. We use pre-trained models to extract features from pet images. These features are then used as input for Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) models to classify pet traits.

Our study has two main goals. First, we test how well different pre-trained CNN models can classify pet traits. This includes models like Xception, VGG16, ResNet50, InceptionV3, MobileNetV2, and NasNetLarge. Also, we evaluate how well new MLP models perform when using feature vectors from pre-trained CNNs. Secondly, we look at how well we can identify different pets by analyzing their features. We use datasets with pictures of dogs, cats, birds, reptiles, and small mammals.

Our study is important because we looked at many different kinds of pets and learned a lot about how to identify them.

pet traits and different models to identify pets, all together. This plan is to make it easier to identify and take care of pets so they can be managed and looked after better. In addition, our research looks at how well pre-trained models for recognizing human faces can also be used to identify pets.

We want to see if these models are good enough for this kind of task.

In summary, we suggest using advanced models to classify pet traits and different models to identify pets, all together. This plan is to make it easier to identify and take care of pets so they can be managed and looked after better.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many studies have looked at using deep learning to recognize different types of pets and individual pets in pictures. This is part of a larger effort to identify animals based on their physical features. In [1] The classification of pets based on identity characteristics, expanding its center past pooches to incorporate other companion creatures like cats, winged creatures, and little warm blooded creatures. It emphasizes the potential of AI and ML strategies in understanding and foreseeing pet behavior over species. Considering person contrasts in pet identities is significant for assessing their appropriateness for families and situations, affecting the quality of the human-animal bond and by and large welfare. By consolidating these strategies into pet behavior inquire about, researchers can progress our understanding of companion creature behavior and illuminate way better pet care hones.

[2] explores the utilization of pre-trained models for extracting biometric information from images of various pets, encompassing attributes such as pet type, breed, birthplace, and skin type. This approach helps in preparing Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) models for exact classification of pet traits. The dataset comprises a assorted extend of pets, counting pooches, cats, feathered creatures, and other family pets, encouraging location and classification of pet sorts and breeds, as well as distinguishing proof of origin and skin sort. Comes about demonstrate the viability of pre-trained models in precisely extricating biometric data, empowering exact classification of pet traits. This investigate contributes to headways in pet care innovation, improving understanding and administration of pets' wellbeing and well-being over diverse species. In expansion, the think about addresses the issue of stray creatures, especially mutts, predominant in different locales due to deficiently information of capable pet care hones among proprietors. Conventional petdistinguishing proof strategies, such as collars or microchips, are exorbitant and inclined to misfortune or harm. To handle this challenge, the think about proposes a non-invasive approach utilizing picture classification frameworks to extricate biometric data specifically from pet pictures. Particularly, pre-trained Convolutional Neural Arrange (CNN) models are utilized to distinguish pet qualities, counting sort, breed, origin, and skin sort. This

approach offers a more productive and comprehensive arrangement for pet distinguishing proof, contributing to successful pet administration and welfare enhancement endeavors.

[3] reviews methods for dog breed classification, noting challenges due to breed diversity. Existing approaches incorporate geometric highlight extraction with machine learning, single convolutional neural network (CNN) models, and CNN combined with machine learning. In any case, these strategies have confinements in exactness and scope of puppy breeds. For occurrence, single CNN models ordinarily accomplish up to 80% exactness. Whereas a few consider combining CNN and machine learning appear moved forward precision, they still drop brief compared to other species classification rates. For case, bloom recognizable proof utilizing CNN and bolster vector machine (SVM) accomplishes 97% precision. This ponder points to upgrade pooch breed classification exactness by joining different CNN models with SVM and utilizing dimensionality lessening and highlight choice procedures. By utilizing the Stanford Puppy Dataset, the proposed strategy accomplishes a classification exactness of 95.24% for 120 breeds and 99.34% for 76 chosen breeds. The think about expects its strategy to serve as a crucial system for precise classification of a broader extend of species.

[4] explores the use of deep learning, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), for identifying dog breeds from facial images. Scientists often use transfer learning to adapt pre-trained CNNs on dog breed datasets that are available to the public. They also use techniques to change and enhance images. The results show that the CNN models like VGG, ResNet, and Inception are between 80% and 90% accurate. Conversations cover how to use the information, problems like unfair data and making ideas work in different situations, and what might happen next, such as using specific structures and combining different types of data. Even though we are making progress, it is still important to deal with unfair opinions and make sure that our ideas apply to a wide range of situations. This will help more people use them in real life

[5] This study looks at how computer programs can use deep learning to identify dogs and their breeds in pictures. CNNs are very good at sorting pictures because they have layers that work together. The experimental results show that the CNN-based approach works well with different sets of data and is very accurate. The survey shows how important CNNs are in machine learning, especially for identifying and recognizing images. The article also talks about how deep convolutional neural networks, like MobileNet, have changed for mobile and embedded vision uses. It shows how these networks have become more accurate and efficient than older models. [6] This study looks at how well adjusting pre-trained models works for identifying dog breeds. It's a common method in deep learning research. Usually, scientists use transfer learning by adjusting pre-trained CNNs and adding different techniques to improve how well the model works.

[6] This study looks at how well adjusting pre-trained models works for identifying dog breeds. It's a common method in deep learning research. Usually, scientists use transfer learning by adjusting pre-trained CNNs and adding different techniques to improve how well the model works. In many different sets of information, research shows that the results are usually very accurate, with a success rate of more than 80%. CNN structures like VGG, ResNet, and Inception are often used. Methods like rotating and scaling images are important for improving how accurately things are sorted.

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ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam

People are talking about how this will affect vets and pet services. They are thinking about problems like biased data and problems with making generalizations. Furthermore, the survey talks about what they might study next, and says that there is still work to do in figuring out the best ways to identify dog breeds. [7] The paper describes a phone app for Android that uses a special kind of computer program and a learning method to recognize different kinds of dogs from pictures. People can take a picture of their dog or upload one, and then the picture gets ready for testing by extracting important parts from it. CNN and transfer learning make it easier to predict the breed of a dog. Training uses Stanford's regular dog information, resulting in an impressive 94% accuracy on testing information. This study shows how we can use deep learning to identify different dog breeds using mobile phones. It helps solve real-life problems. [8] This study looks at a new way to tell what kind of dog it is using a computer program. It combines a few different methods to do this, like using a special kind of math called Principal Component Analysis, a type of computer program called a Convolutional Neural Network, an algorithm called Gray Wolf Optimization, and another computer program called Support Vector Machine. Although it can be hard to accurately identify dog breeds, a new method has been successful. It can identify 120 dog breeds with 95.24% accuracy using the Stanford Dog Dataset. The research shows that using advanced methods to find important features and improve how they work could help classify different species better. It also suggests ideas for more research in this area.

These research studies give us a good understanding of the ways and tools used to identify different pet types, breeds and individual pets. This can help develop better systems for pet identification.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Data Collection and Preprocessing: The system starts by gathering basic information including pictures of pets from different places.

Preprocessing methods are used to clean and get the data ready for more analysis. This helps make sure the data is all the same and works well together.

Feature Extraction: This is about finding and selecting important information from data.

The important information is taken from the filtered data, like the kind of animal, what it looks like, and where it was born. Sophisticated computer programs are used to find important parts of pictures of pets, making it easier to sort them correctly.

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) Architecture:

A Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is a type of computer program that is used for processing and analyzing visual data. We use a VGG-16 model that has been trained before as the main design of our system, which helps to extract features effectively.

To make it more accurate and flexible, we added more layers with a certain kind of activation function to improve the features.

The CNN design is adjusted and trained more using a lot of pet pictures to make it work even better.

Detection and Output:

Once the training and testing are done, the model is ready to be used.

The model can accurately tell the breed, type, skin traits, and where a pet was born by looking at a picture of it.

The system gives a lot of information, like what kind of pet is in the picture.

These studies give us a good understanding of the ways used to identify dog breeds and individual dogs. This information can help us create better systems for identifying dogs.

Screenshots:

Figure 1 : User interface

Figure 2 : Image Uploading

Figure 3 : Image detection results

Figure 4 : Image detection results

Figure 5 : Result.

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V CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our utilization of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for pet breed prediction has yielded promising outcomes. CNNs are really good at figuring out what's in a picture, and our system uses them to predict what type of pets there are. We want to include all types of pets like dogs, cats, and birds in our system to make it more useful and have a bigger effect. We used transfer learning and made specialized classification layers for each type of pet. This made our model much more accurate. In the future, we see more progress in predicting the breeds of pets by improving our methods. This will make our system better at working with different kinds of pets. Our method makes it easy for users to ask questions and get quick answers based on the information they provide.

This study shows that paying attention to context is really important for making question-answering models work well. In addition, the results show that these models could be used to make chatbots better in real life situations. Future studies may explore using different models and data to improve the accuracy and effectiveness of these systems.

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